

FEDORA

Deliverable 6.5

FEDORA Podcast

Due date: August 31st 2022

Actual submission date: August 31st 2022

Project start date: Sept 1st 2020

Work Package concerned: WP6

Concerned Work Package leader: formicablu

Task leader: formicablu

Dissemination level:

- PU: Public

Quality assurance

To ensure the quality and correctness of this deliverable, we implied an internal review and validation process. The deliverable was drafted by the work package leader (formicablu). All partners contributed to and reviewed the overall draft. Finally, the semi-final version was submitted to the project coordinator for a final review and validation.

Version	Date	Status	Author	
V0	24/08/2022	Draft and internal revision	formicablu Elisabetta Tola, F. Conti	Creation of the document
V1	29/08/2022	Submitted to Coordinator	formicablu E. Tola, F. Conti; andrea Troncoso, Emma D'Orto	Peer review
V2	31/08/2022	Submitted in the Portal	Coordinator	Final version

Disclaimer

This deliverable contains original, unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. It builds upon the experience of the team and related work published on this topic. Acknowledgement of previously published material and others' work has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.

The views and opinions expressed in this publication are the authors' sole responsibility and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

Table of Contents

1. Summary
2. Introduction
3. Editorial plan
4. Dissemination and trailer

1. Summary

As part of the original voice that the FEDORA project has set as a purpose for reaching its audiences in a compelling and meaningful way, the “FEDORA podcast” is a communication tool that will share the views, narratives and questions that the project intends to address.

Deliverable 6.5 “FEDORA podcast” explains the aim of this dissemination product, as well as its editorial plan and shares a trailer that invites and explains the contents of the series of audios that will be released between September 2022 and June 2023.

This deliverable is the 5th document delivered by WP6 “Behind the scenes: Communicating and Disseminating FEDORA in its making”, part of task 6.4 “Multimedia production”, and is led by formicablu.

2. Introduction

FEDORA's Work Package 6 "Behind the scenes" considers the production of multimedia products that encourage and inspire attitudes toward open schooling and future-oriented science education. This series of podcasts contributes to this aim, sharing the voices behind the ideas, the practice and theories pertaining to the development of the project.

The rise of digital science communication platforms has presented new opportunities and of course new challenges. Among the opportunities, podcasts have raised as a new channel for communicating diverse topics by a myriad of science communicators¹. Podcasts belong to the new ways science communication is consumed and produced at the same time.

Podcasts have become a popular way of science communication as they are flexible in their format, they can reach a wide audience, their dissemination is uncomplicated and often they are not cost-intensive.

FEDORA podcasts will be a series of five 15-minute long episodes produced by the communication team with the contribution of the whole consortium. They will provide a narrated description and analysis of FEDORA's main objectives, actions and findings. It will include interviews with FEDORA researchers and partners, as well as with stakeholders and players in the specific activities carried on throughout the project. The podcast content will be enriched with findings and results coming from each Work Package. Although educational in its main objectives and targets, the podcast series will have a strong storytelling register and will be formatted to be distributed on podcast platforms such as Soundcloud, iTunes, Spotify, Spreaker or Voxnest.

¹ Fährlich B, Wilkinson C, Weitkamp E, Heintz L, Ridgway A and Milani E (2021) RETHINKING Science Communication Education and Training: Towards a Competence Model for Science Communication. *Front. Commun.* 6:795198. doi: 10.3389/fcomm.2021.795198

3. Editorial plan

FEDORA will produce a 2-minute trailer and 5 episodes 15-minute long each, to be published in the following months:

- Podcast 1: October 2022
- Podcast 2: December 2022
- Podcast 3: February 2023
- Podcast 4: April 2023
- Podcast 5: June 2023

Each episode will portray 2 voices: one of a FEDORA partner and one of an independent external expert, so that we complement the work done in Fedora with indications, insights, ideas, suggestions, evaluations made by others. Since it is challenging to interview two different people at the same time, we plan to record 2 separate interviews and then post-produce the conversation.

The editing approach will be to select extracts from the conversations, building a narrative path that reflects a story, in a way that allows the listener to understand the different perspectives. With this pre-script, the communication team will record texts that will connect those extracts, sometimes with questions, or reflections in order to create a sound melody of the content. These texts will be the main skeleton where all the contributions will be embedded and inserted, in an order that is not necessarily that of the original conversation but rather follows the narrative we want to propose.

The partners that will be participating as interviewees are the following:

- Olivia Levrini, University of Bologna
- Erica Bol, Teach the Future
- Sibel Erduran, University of Oxford
- Antti Laherto, University of Helsinki
- Raminta Pucetaite, Kaunas University of Technology
- Giulia Tasquier, University of Bologna

Independent experts will be also invited to contribute. The following experts will be considered as possible interviewees:

- Baiba Pruse, Ca' Foscari University of Venice
- Egle Butkeviciene, University of Kaunas
- Jelle de Schrijver, University of Antwerp
- Damian Hebron, Wellcome Connecting Science
- Sam Illingworth, Edinburgh Napier University

-
- Carlo Maver, Musician

Each episode will focus on the following FEDORA driving ideas:

- Blind spots and change
- Creativity and open schooling
- Futurisation
- Interdisciplinarity
- Epistemic skills

4. Dissemination and trailer

The podcast will be recorded with professional equipment and the interviews will be run either online or face-to-face, depending on the location of the interviewees. The trailer and the full episodes will be edited with the software Adobe Audition and Adobe Premiere Pro.

To maximise the reach, we will utilise SoundCloud and explore other platforms like Spreaker, Spotify, Itunes and Voxnest, in order to maximize the reach.

The trailer was recorded by the communications team. It describes in a brief and engaging way the content of the series of podcasts and why it is worth listening to. The trailer is available here: <https://soundcloud.com/fedora-project>